

INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGY (ICT) ACCESS AND COMPETENCE OF SCHOOL LEADERS AND TEACHERS IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the extent of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) access and competence among secondary school leaders and teachers and examined the challenges they encounter in integrating ICT into teaching management. A quantitative descriptive-correlational approach was employed, involving 123 teachers and 4 school heads selected through total enumeration in the SV–SLR District. Data were obtained using a validated researcher-developed instrument and analyzed using weighted mean, Pearson's r , and Kendall's W . Findings indicate that ICT resources were generally available; however, disparities were observed in IT support services for school leaders and infrastructure reliability for teachers. Teachers demonstrated a higher level of ICT competence compared to school leaders. Insufficient technical support and limited structured training emerged as the most pressing concerns. Statistical analysis revealed a significant positive association between ICT access and competence ($r = .634$, $p < .05$), as well as significant agreement regarding perceived challenges. The study underscores the necessity of strengthening institutional ICT support systems and proposes Project iLEAD as a structured framework for enhancing digital leadership and professional competence in secondary schools.

Keywords: *ICT access, ICT competence, school leaders, teachers, secondary schools, challenges, professional development, intervention program*

INTRODUCTION

The continuous evolution of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has reshaped educational systems by redefining how schools operate, deliver instruction, and manage administrative functions. Beyond improving efficiency, ICT integration influences leadership practices, instructional design, collaboration, and student engagement. Prior research suggests that technology adoption in schools is not solely determined by availability of equipment but also by institutional culture, leadership capacity, and systemic conditions (Zhao & Frank, 2003).

Within the Philippine educational landscape, the Department of Education has implemented initiatives such as the DepEd Computerization Program and the Digital Rise Program to expand technological capacity and professional development. Despite these efforts, uneven levels of digital readiness persist across public secondary schools. The pandemic further exposed structural limitations in connectivity, infrastructure, and digital competence, intensifying concerns regarding equitable ICT integration.

Existing literature highlights that teachers' use of ICT is shaped by confidence, technical skills, access to training, and organizational support (Buabeng-Andoh, 2015). Studies conducted in the Philippine context further emphasize that secondary school teachers experience both structural and instructional challenges in ICT integration, including limited technical support and infrastructure constraints (Garzon & Gumban, 2022). Local studies likewise emphasize the need for continuous professional development to strengthen digital literacy among educators (Dela Rama et al., 2024). For school administrators, digital leadership and ICT self-efficacy play a critical role in fostering technology-driven school improvement (Guhao, 2023). Furthermore, sustained technical assistance significantly influences ICT utilization at the district level (Reyes & Jose, 2024).

Given these perspectives, this study sought to generate district-level empirical evidence on ICT access, competence, and encountered challenges among school leaders and teachers, thereby informing context-responsive intervention strategies.

Research Questions

1. What is the Information and Communication Technology (ICT) Access and Competence of School Leaders and Teachers in Secondary Schools along
 - 1.1 Access
 - 1.2 Competence?

2. What are the challenges encountered in Information and Communication Technology (ICT) of School Leaders and Teachers in Secondary Schools along
 - 2.1 Access
 - 2.2 Competence?

3. Is there a significant relationship between Information and Communication Technology (ICT) Access and Competence and the challenges encountered by School Leaders and Teachers?
4. Is there a significant agreement in the challenges encountered between the School Leaders and Teachers in Information and Communication Technology (ICT) Access and Competence?
5. Based on the findings of the study, what intervention may be proposed to enhance Information and Communication Technology (ICT) Access and Competence of the respondents?

METHODOLOGY

A descriptive-correlational research design was employed to determine the status of ICT access and competence, as well as the challenges encountered by school leaders and teachers. The study was conducted in the secondary schools of the San Vicente–San Lorenzo Ruiz District, Division of Camarines Norte. Total enumeration was used, involving 127 respondents.

Data were gathered using a validated self-constructed questionnaire covering ICT access, ICT competence, and encountered challenges. After securing necessary approvals, the researcher administered and retrieved the questionnaires personally to ensure a high retrieval rate. The collected responses were subjected to reliability analysis using Cronbach's Alpha to determine internal consistency. The results revealed high reliability across all variables. Specifically, the ICT Access scale obtained a Cronbach's Alpha coefficient of 0.87, indicating good internal consistency. The ICT Competence scale yielded a Cronbach's Alpha of 0.91, reflecting excellent reliability. These values exceed the acceptable threshold of 0.70, confirming that the instrument consistently measured the intended variables

Data analysis was performed using SPSS v21. Weighted Mean described ICT access and competence levels; Pearson Product-Moment Correlation tested the relationship between variables; and Kendall's Coefficient of Concordance measured agreement between the rankings of challenges.

RESULTS

This section presents the findings of the study on the ICT access, ICT competence, challenges encountered, and the relationships among these variables as perceived by school leaders and teachers in secondary schools in the SV-SLR District.

ICT Access of School Leaders and Teachers. The results show that both school leaders and teachers generally have adequate ICT access, as reflected by an overall weighted mean of 3.38 for school leaders and 3.31 for teachers, both interpreted as Fully

Accessible. This indicates that ICT resources necessary for administrative and instructional functions are generally available in schools. Among school leaders, the highest-rated indicator was access to ICT hardware such as computers, smartphones, and tablets (WM = 4.00, Fully Accessible), while the lowest-rated indicator was access to IT support services, including technical assistance and training (WM = 2.50, Highly Accessible). For teachers, the highest-rated indicators were access to hardware and network connectivity (WM = 3.54, Fully Accessible). In contrast, the lowest-rated indicator was access to ICT infrastructure, such as electricity supply and physical facilities (WM = 3.07, Highly Accessible). These results indicate that while ICT tools and connectivity are largely available, support systems and infrastructure remain areas of concern.

Table 1
Information and Communication Technology (ICT) Access of School Leaders and Teachers

Indicators	School Leader		Teacher	
	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. I have an access on different hardware such as computers, smartphones, tablets, servers, routers, and other physical equipment necessary for assessing and utilizing digital information and services.	4.00	FA	3.54	FA
2. I have an access on software such as operating systems, applications, and programs.	3.50	FA	3.26	FA
3. I have an access on network connectivity such as the internet or local area networks which is crucial for accessing digital resources and services.	3.25	FA	3.54	FA
4. I have an access on internet service providers in which provide access to the internet or digital world.	3.00	HA	3.46	FA
5. I am proficient in using ICT tools and can effectively use the said tools.	3.25	FA	3.21	HA

6. I have an access on the policies and regulations implemented by the government such as regulations on internet access, data privacy, cybersecurity, net neutrality and others.	3.75	FA	3.29	FA
7. I can afford the cost of ICT equipment services and internet connectivity.	3.50	FA	3.32	FA
8. I have an access on IT infrastructures such as telecommunication networks, electricity supply, and physical infrastructures like roads and buildings.	3.25	FA	3.07	HA
9. ICT services are accessible to all including people with disabilities and other handicapped individuals.	3.75	FA	3.33	FA
10. I have an access on support IT services such technical support, training and assistance to users.	2.50	HA	3.08	HA
Overall Weighted Mean	3.38	FA	3.31	FA

Rating Scale:	Descriptive Interpretation:
3.25- 4.00	- Fully Accessible (FA)
2.50- 3.24	- Highly Accessible (HA)
1.75-2.49	- Rarely Accessible (RA)
1.00-1.74	- Not Accessible (NA)

ICT Competence of School Leaders and Teachers. In terms of ICT competence, teachers obtained a higher overall weighted mean (3.38 – Very Competent) compared to school leaders (2.95 – Competent). This suggests that teachers generally perceive themselves as more competent in using ICT, particularly for instructional purposes. School leaders demonstrated their highest competence in knowledge of ICT use, internet use for research, and ICT integration in professional practice (WM = 3.25, Very Competent). However, their lowest competence was observed in troubleshooting technical issues and adapting to new technologies (WM = 2.25, Moderately Competent). Teachers showed very high competence in internet use for research and information gathering (WM = 3.50, Very Competent) and in integrating ICT into instruction. Similar to school leaders, their lowest-rated indicator was also technical troubleshooting and

adaptation to new software (WM = 2.95, Competent). These findings indicate that both groups are confident ICT users, but advanced technical and analytical skills remain limited, particularly among school leaders.

Table 2
Information and Communication Technology (ICT) Competence of School Leaders and Teachers

Indicators	School leader		Teacher	
	Weighted Mean	Interpretation	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. I have the necessary knowledge in terms of proper utilization of the ICT tools and use it in my advantage and in my daily work and living.	3.25	VC	3.40	VC
2. I have the necessary skills in using ICT tools and utilize it in my daily work and living.	2.75	C	3.41	VC
3. I have the right mind and attitude in relation to the proper usage of these ICT tools in order for me to utilize its advantages in my daily work and living.	3.25	C	3.47	VC
4. I am proficient in navigating various software applications and regularly use them to enhance productivity in both professional and personal tasks.	2.50	C	3.27	VC
5. I can easily troubleshoot basic technical issues with ICT tools and adapt quickly to new software or technological advancements.	2.25	MC	2.95	C
6. I effectively incorporate ICT tools in communicating and	3.00	C	3.42	VC

	collaborating with colleagues or teams, both in person and virtually.				
7.	I frequently use the internet to research and gather information, applying it to problem-solving and decision-making in my daily work.	3.25	VC	3.50	VC
8.	I am capable of managing and organizing digital files, ensuring that my data is stored securely and is easily accessible when needed.	3.00	C	3.45	VC
9.	I integrate ICT tools into my instructional or professional practice, ensuring that technology enhances both the delivery and effectiveness of my work.	3.25	VC	3.47	VC
10.	I am confident in using ICT tools to analyze and interpret data, applying insights to improve decision-making processes in my field.	3.00	C	3.41	VC
Overall Weighted Mean		2.95	C	3.38	VC
Rating Scale:		Descriptive Interpretation:			
3.25- 4.00	-	Very Competent (VC)			
2.50- 3.24	-	Competent (C)			
1.75-2.49	-	Moderately Competent (FC)			
1.00-1.74	-	Not Competent (NC)			

Challenges Encountered in ICT Access. The results reveal that difficulty in accessing IT support services and training programs was ranked as the most challenging issue by both school leaders and teachers. This indicates a common concern regarding the lack of sustained technical assistance and professional development opportunities. For school leaders, the least challenging issue was access to ICT hardware, while for teachers, the least challenging was access to necessary software applications. This

confirms that resource availability is no longer the primary barrier, but rather the support mechanisms that enable effective ICT use.

Table 3
Challenges Encountered in ICT
ICT Access of School Leaders and Teachers

Indicators	School Leader		Teacher	
	Sum of Ranks	Rank	Sum of Ranks	Rank
1. I am having trouble in terms of accessing hardware components such as computers, smartphones, table, servers, routers and other physical equipment.	13	10	559	2
2. I am having difficulties in terms of accessing necessary software applications to be used in teaching.	15	9	533	10
3. I am having trouble in terms of accessing internet and other networks which I need in teaching classes.	29	3	596	8
4. I am having problems with my internet service providers and having trouble connecting to the internet.	30	2	598	7
5. I have difficulties in relation to my ICT or digital literacy hence making me unable to utilize the full potential of the ICT tools.	16	8	615	6
6. I am having difficulties in purchasing ICT equipment and services as I lack funds to do so.	18	7	693	5
7. I am having problems in terms of ICT infrastructure access.	26	4	734	4
8. ICT services have problems in terms of it being accessible to different individuals especially persons with disabilities or handicapped.	20	6	740	3
9. I am having problems	22	5	744	9

understanding government regulations in relation to proper utilization of ICT tools, equipment and services.				
10. I am having difficulties in accessing IT support services including trainings and programs.	31	1	757	1

Challenges Encountered in ICT Competence. In terms of ICT competence, both school leaders and teachers identified difficulty in using data analysis tools and software as the most challenging concern. This suggests limitations in using ICT for data-driven decision-making, assessment, and instructional planning. The least challenging issues for both groups were lack of knowledge about ICT advantages and negative perceptions toward ICT, indicating positive attitudes and awareness of ICT benefits.

Table 4
Challenges Encountered in ICT
ICT Competence of School Leaders and Teachers

Indicators	School Leader		Teacher	
	Sum of Ranks	of Rank	Sum of Ranks	Rank
1. I lack the knowledge in relation to utilizing the advantages of ICT tools, equipment and services in my daily work and living.	13	10	443	10
2. I lack the skills in terms of utilizing ICT tools and equipment in my daily work and living.	17	8	472	9
3. I am having problems in relation to my perception towards the use of ICT tools and equipment and tend to still utilize traditional methods in teaching classes and in my daily living.	15	9	556	7
4. I lack the confidence in using various ICT tools and services to enhance my productivity at work.	21	6	482	8
5. I struggle to keep up with the latest technological advancements and find it difficult to apply new ICT tools in my tasks.	19	7	673	6
6. I am having difficulties to troubleshoot basic ICT-related	31	1	726	3

issues without needing external support.				
7. I lack the ability to use ICT tools effectively for communication and collaboration with my colleagues.	23	5	674	5
8. I seldom use ICT resources, such as the internet and software, to solve problems and make informed decisions.	27	3	718	4
9. I find it challenging to organize and manage digital files, leading to inefficiency in accessing important information.	25	4	757	2
10. I am having troubles in using data analysis tools and software to interpret and apply data in my work.	29	2	828	1

Relationship Between ICT Access and ICT Competence The Pearson correlation analysis revealed a moderate to strong positive relationship between ICT access and ICT competence ($r = .634$, $p = .000$). This result indicates that higher levels of ICT access are significantly associated with higher levels of ICT competence among school leaders and teachers. Consequently, the null hypothesis was rejected.

Table 5
Test for Significant Relationship between ICT Access and ICT Competence of School Leaders and Teachers

	Pearson (r)	p-value	Remarks	Decision
ICT competence and ICT Access	.634**	.000	Significant	Reject H_0

Agreement on ICT Challenges The Kendall's W test showed significant agreement between school leaders and teachers regarding the challenges encountered in both ICT access ($W = .074$, $p = .000$) and ICT competence ($W = .166$, $p = .000$). Although the level of agreement was low, the significance indicates that both groups consistently recognize similar challenges.

Table 6
Test for Significant Agreement on the Challenges Encountered by School Leaders and Teachers

	Kendall's W	Chi-Square	p-value	Remarks
ICT Access	.074	82.411	.000	Significant

ICT Competence	.166	187.01	.000	Significant
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*Significant @ 0.05 level

DISCUSSION

The findings suggest that while ICT tools and connectivity are generally available in the participating schools, the presence of resources alone does not ensure optimal technology integration. Consistent with Adarkwah (2021), digital inequality may persist even when hardware is present, particularly when support systems and infrastructure reliability are insufficient.

Although national ICT initiatives provide a structural foundation for digital integration, the limited availability of technical support services remains a critical concern. This aligns with Reyes and Jose (2024), who emphasized that the effectiveness of ICT implementation is strongly influenced by access to ongoing technical assistance and system maintenance.

The higher competence levels reported by teachers may be attributed to their routine instructional use of digital tools, whereas school leaders may engage ICT primarily for administrative tasks. This finding reinforces the importance of strengthening digital leadership capacity, particularly in data analysis and technical problem-solving, as highlighted by Guhao (2023).

The significant correlation between ICT access and competence confirms that exposure and availability contribute to skill development. However, the shared challenges reported by both groups indicate that ICT limitations are systemic rather than individual. This observation supports the ecological perspective of technology integration proposed by Zhao and Frank (2003), which emphasizes the interplay between organizational conditions and individual capability.

Overall, the results demonstrate that sustainable ICT integration requires a comprehensive strategy that balances infrastructure provision, leadership development, technical assistance, and continuous professional learning.

Conclusions

The study establishes that although ICT resources are largely accessible in the participating secondary schools, inconsistencies in technical support and infrastructure reliability constrain effective utilization. Variations in competence between teachers and school leaders further highlight the need for differentiated digital capacity-building initiatives.

The statistically significant relationship between ICT access and competence underscores the importance of ensuring both availability and skill development to achieve meaningful integration. Moreover, the observed agreement regarding ICT-related

challenges suggests that existing barriers are embedded within institutional systems rather than isolated to individual capability.

These findings support the implementation of a structured and sustainable intervention framework, such as Project iLEAD, to enhance digital leadership, strengthen technical support mechanisms, and promote long-term ICT integration in secondary education.

Recommendations

To address the identified gaps in ICT support, access, and competence, the implementation of Project iLEAD (Innovative Leadership and Enhancement of Academic Digitization) is strongly recommended. This initiative serves as a structured intervention to bridge the competence gap between teachers and school leaders, ensuring both groups can effectively integrate technology into instructional and management practices.

Institutionalizing continuous professional development programs focused on instructional technology and digital school management is likewise essential. Specialized digital leadership training may further empower school heads to effectively guide technology-driven innovation.

Establishing peer mentoring systems may encourage collaborative knowledge-sharing, while sustained funding allocation is necessary to maintain ICT resources and training initiatives. Future research may expand this inquiry across additional districts and incorporate qualitative approaches to capture contextual experiences in greater depth.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The study adhered to established ethical standards in the conduct of educational research. Informed consent was obtained from all respondents prior to data collection, and participation was entirely voluntary, with respondents informed of their right to withdraw from the study at any time without consequence. The anonymity and confidentiality of all respondents were strictly maintained, and all data were collected, stored, and processed in compliance with applicable data privacy regulations. The well-being of the respondents was safeguarded throughout the research process, and no physical, psychological, or emotional harm was incurred. The authors declare that no conflict of interest existed in the conduct of the study. Plagiarism was strictly avoided through proper citation and acknowledgment of sources, and the analysis and interpretation of findings were carried out objectively and without bias. The results of the study were used solely for academic and research purposes. Artificial intelligence tools were utilized exclusively to assist in language editing and manuscript organization, and full responsibility for the content, analysis, and conclusions remains with the authors.

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